

1 CDK4/6 inhibitor in conjunction with proliferation-based imaging or assay for synthetic lethal
2 pharmacologic management of chronic disease initiation.

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 Public health management requires a concerted effort involving detection in the community. We propose
8 here a general method of inducing synthetic lethality in any cells undergoing proliferative expansion
9 resulting from endogenous mutation or viral infection via -cyclib CDK4/6 inhibition.

10 Citations

11 1. Allison, S.J., 2020. Synthetic lethality between loss of CDK4/6 activity and VHL inactivation.
12 Nature Reviews Nephrology, 16(1), pp.2-2.

13 2. Nicholson, H.E., Tariq, Z., Housden, B.E., Jennings, R.B., Stransky, L.A., Perrimon, N., Signoretti,
14 S., Harris, I.S., Endress, J.E. and Kaelin Jr, W.G., 2019. HIF-independent synthetic lethality between
15 CDK4/6 inhibition and VHL loss across species. Science signaling, 12(601), p.eaay0482.

16 3. Feng, M., Liu, H., Zheng, L., Liu, Y., Zhuang, H., Xu, H., Zhang, T., Wu, Z., Qian, X., Li, H. and
17 Xiao, T., 2026. Genome-wide screenings identify BAP1 as a synthetic-lethality target with CDK4/6
18 inhibitors. Science Advances, 12(3), p.eaeb4348.

19 4. Divakar, S.K.A., Reddy, R., Cosenza, S.C., Baker, S.J., Perumal, D., Antonelli, A.C., Brody, J.,
20 Akula, B., Parekh, S. and Premkumar Reddy, E., 2016. Dual inhibition of CDK4/Rb and PI3K/AKT/mTOR
21 pathways by ON123300 induces synthetic lethality in mantle cell lymphomas. Leukemia, 30(1), pp.86-93.

22 5. Zhang, R., Yang, J. and Chen, C., 2018. Tumor cell identification in ki-67 images on deep
23 learning. Molecular & Cellular Biomechanics, 15(3), p.177.

24 6. Bading, J.R. and Shields, A.F., 2008. Imaging of cell proliferation: status and prospects. Journal of
25 Nuclear Medicine, 49(Suppl 2), pp.64S-80S.